

Mid-infrared OCT for non-destructive sub-surface inspection and in-line production monitoring

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Near-infrared optical coherence tomography (NIR OCT) allows for non-destructive detection and imaging. The technology is often used for medical purposes and for biology research such as delineating cellular interfaces or inclusions inside the human retina [1]. Although OCT was established more than 30 years ago and is well established, sample penetration remains a key limitation. While utilizing a sample probe wavelength above $2\ \mu\text{m}$ wavelength could reduce tissue scattering and enable deeper penetration, water absorption does not allow such an option. In non-destructive inspection (NDI) of industrial materials, water is often not present and increasing the probe wavelength to reduce scattering becomes interesting. With reduced scattering, a Mid-infrared OCT (MIR OCT) system has the ability to measure deeper structures compared to the NIR OCT counterpart. In industrial NDI there is a need for fast, non-destructive, non-contact and production integrated detection to ensure that the manufacturing follows performance-defined specifications [2,3]. With the current industrial agenda of reducing the CO₂ footprint, there is an increasing demand for in-line inspection of component and material production. In this work, we report examples of how OCT using light of around $4\ \mu\text{m}$ wavelength can act as a powerful tool for in-line inspection in the production.

Fig. 1 shows an example of MIR OCT characterisation of a 3D printed sample. The perspective here is to set-up in-line monitoring of 3D printing performance. Fig. 1(a) shows a schematic of the MIR OCT system. The source is a supercontinuum laser coupled with a ZBLAN fiber providing a spectrum from $0.8\ \mu\text{m}$ to $4.5\ \mu\text{m}$. The interferometer is based on Michelson design. After the interferometer, the output light passes through an upconversion stage to convert the spectrum to 820-870 nm which allows fast silicon based detection [4]. Fig. 1(b) shows an illustration of the 3D printed sample tested. The sample is an epoxy resin cube with air holes running through it. The cube was printed with stereolithography (SLA) method in transparent resin. Its size is $10\times 10\times 10\ \text{mm}^3$, and the size of the holes is $400\times 400\ \mu\text{m}$. Fig. 1(c) and 1(d) show, respectively, the B-scan and the C-scan of the cube over a $6\times 6\ \text{mm}^2$ surface. In both views, we detect the signature of the top and bottom air/resin interface of 7 holes. In this example, it appears that one hole is misprinted, this is maybe due to a problem during the 3D printing process or during the flushing.

Fig. 1 (a) MIR OCT schematic. The system is divided in five parts: a supercontinuum MIR source, a Michelson interferometer, an xy scan head, an upconversion and detection module and the in-line production monitoring [3], (b) 3D illustration of the 3D printed cube tested with a honey comb holes inside. Cube size : $10\times 10\times 10\ \text{mm}^3$. Size of the holes : $400\times 400\ \mu\text{m}$, (c) Bscan view of the tested cube, (d) 3D visualisation of the full OCT scan and (e) is the top interface air/resin. In (c,d,e) A, B, C, D are respectively the cube surface, the top interface, the bottom interface and a hole misprinted.

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